

Thermodynamic properties of binary liquid mixtures containing 1,2-ethanediol and primary alcohols at different temperature

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Abstract : Densities and viscosities of the binary mixtures of 1,2-ethanediol with primary alcohols such as methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol and 1-butanol were measured at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K and refractive index for same systems were measured at 303.15 K over the entire composition range. This experimental data were used to calculate excess molar volumes (V^E), viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and refractive index deviations (Δn_D). These results were fitted to Redlich-Kister polynomial equation and results have been discussed in terms of molecular interaction and structural effects. The excess properties were found to be either positive or negative depending on the molecular interaction and the nature of liquid mixtures.

Keywords : Binary mixtures, primary alcohols, 1,2-ethanediol.

Introduction

Studies on thermodynamic properties are important in understanding the molecular interaction in binary liquids mixtures. Thermodynamic properties of mixed solvent systems and their dependence on composition find applications in much important chemical, industrial and biological process¹. The studies of excess functions of binary liquid mixtures are useful in understanding the nature and strength of molecular interactions between the component molecules. 1,2-Ethanediol is a simplest homologue of the diol, largely utilized as thermo regulator fluid, as a controlling agent of density/viscosity/reaction baths, and as emulsion coating due to its unusual physicochemical properties. It is an alcohol with two -OH groups and widely used as automotive antifreeze². Aliphatic alcohols also find wide applications in pharmaceutical

industries. Alcohols are highly self associated through hydrogen bonding and protic in nature. These are versatile solvents used in the separation of saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons and in pharmaceutical synthesis and serves as solvent for many polymers^{3,4}. In the present paper we report density (ρ), viscosity (η) and refractive index (n_D) for the binary mixtures of 1,2-ethanediol with primary alcohols at different temperatures and at atmospheric pressure. The calculated excess quantities from such data have been interpreted in terms of molecular interactions and structural effects.

Results and discussion

The comparison of physical properties of various pure liquids along with their literature values at 303.15 K are recorded in Table 1. The density, viscosity, refractive

Table 1. Comparison of experimental densities, viscosities and refractive indices of pure liquid with literature values at 303.15 K

Pure liquids	ρ (g cm ⁻³)		η (mPa.s)		n_D	
	Expt.	Lit.	Expt.	Lit.	Expt.	Lit.
1,2-Ethanediol	1.10577	1.10546 ¹⁴	13.3461	13.8678 ¹⁴	1.4293	1.4287 ¹⁴
Methanol	0.78174	0.78191 ¹⁹	0.5080	0.5030 ¹⁵	1.3271	1.3272 ¹⁸
Ethanol	0.78069	0.78069 ¹⁶	0.9891	0.9930 ¹⁶	1.3606	-
1-Propanol	0.79583	0.79580 ¹⁵	1.6747	1.7190 ¹⁷	1.3816	-
1-Butanol	0.80190	0.80194 ¹⁶	2.2744	2.2740 ¹⁷	1.3954	1.3957 ¹⁸

index and their excess properties as excess molar volumes, viscosity deviations and refractive index deviations for binary mixtures are presented in Tables 2 to 4.

The excess molar volumes of binary mixtures were calculated by using equation,

$$V^E = ((x_1M_1 + x_2M_2)/\rho) - (x_1V_1 + x_2V_2) \quad (1)$$

where, x_1 , x_2 , M_1 , M_2 , V_1 and V_2 are mole fractions,

Table-2 (contd.)

x_1	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	V^E (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)					
					0.9122	1.08071	18.3860	0.1598	-0.8300
					1.0000	1.11348	20.9490	0.0000	0.0000
					1,2-Ethanediol + 1-propanol				
					0.0000	0.80364	1.9433	0.0000	0.0001
					0.0647	0.81744	2.3526	0.1251	-0.8200
					0.1296	0.83207	2.9272	0.2203	-1.4800
					0.1949	0.84746	3.6470	0.2969	-2.0000
					0.2604	0.86364	4.5222	0.3567	-2.3700
					0.3262	0.88066	5.5427	0.4004	-2.6000
					0.3923	0.89868	6.6786	0.4204	-2.7200
					0.4586	0.91760	7.9599	0.4298	-2.7000
					0.5253	0.93764	9.3166	0.4180	-2.6100
					0.5922	0.95877	10.7688	0.3931	-2.4300
					0.6594	0.98109	12.2965	0.3544	-2.1800
					0.7270	1.00465	13.9198	0.3047	-1.8400
					0.7948	1.02962	15.6186	0.2403	-1.4300
					0.8629	1.05603	17.3731	0.1663	-0.9700
					0.9313	1.08406	19.1732	0.0799	-0.4700
					1.0000	1.11348	20.9490	0.0000	0.0000
					1,2-Ethanediol + 1-butanol				
					0.0000	0.80953	2.9433	0.0000	0.0001
					0.0786	0.82369	3.5483	0.0910	-0.8100
					0.1552	0.83849	4.3678	0.1658	-1.3700
					0.2299	0.85402	5.3028	0.2203	-1.7800
					0.3028	0.87033	6.3548	0.2554	-2.0400
					0.3739	0.88745	7.5048	0.2742	-2.1700
					0.4432	0.90535	8.7241	0.2848	-2.2000
					0.5110	0.92414	10.0138	0.2829	-2.1300
					0.5771	0.94383	11.3548	0.2732	-1.9800
					0.6417	0.96454	12.7282	0.2522	-1.7700
					0.7049	0.98631	14.0949	0.2228	-1.5400
					0.7666	1.00915	15.4959	0.1900	-1.2500
					0.8269	1.03320	16.8820	0.1502	-0.9500
					0.8859	1.05859	18.2540	0.1020	-0.6400
					0.9436	1.08525	19.6128	0.0553	-0.3200
					1.0000	1.11348	20.9490	0.0000	0.0000
					1,2-Ethanediol + ethanol				
					0.0000	0.78923	1.2083	0.0000	0.0000
					0.0503	0.80348	1.4322	0.0997	-0.7700
					0.1025	0.81832	1.7814	0.1982	-1.4500
					0.1565	0.83386	2.2479	0.2904	-2.0500
					0.2125	0.85038	2.8539	0.3601	-2.5500
					0.2707	0.86761	3.6113	0.4296	-2.9400
					0.3310	0.88589	4.5428	0.4797	-3.2000
					0.3937	0.90525	5.6208	0.5130	-3.3600
					0.4589	0.92576	6.8682	0.5299	-3.4000
					0.5268	0.94751	8.2879	0.5299	-3.3200
					0.5975	0.97068	9.9232	0.5079	-3.0800
					0.6712	0.99545	11.7277	0.4597	-2.7300
					0.7480	1.02187	13.8051	0.3899	-2.1700
					0.8283	1.05023	15.9597	0.2901	-1.6000

molecular weights and molar volumes of first and second components respectively.

Dynamic viscosities (η) of binary mixtures of 1,2-ethanediol (1) + primary alcohols (2) were calculated by using densities and flow times by equation,

$$\eta = K.p.(t-HC) \quad (2)$$

where, K and p are viscometer constant and density of

Table 3. Values of density, viscosity, refractive index and excess properties of binary liquid mixtures of 1,2-ethanediol with primary alcohols at 303.15 K

x_1	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	n_D	V^E (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	Δn_D
1,2-Ethanediol + methanol						
0.0000	0.78174	0.5080	1.3271	0.0000	0.0001	0.0000
0.0356	0.79617	0.6375	1.3440	0.0598	-0.3269	0.0087
0.0736	0.81106	0.7627	1.3516	0.1280	-0.6898	0.0158
0.1143	0.82625	0.8755	1.3625	0.2150	-1.0998	0.0223
0.1580	0.84235	1.0571	1.3728	0.2913	-1.4798	0.0291
0.2052	0.85935	1.3218	1.3832	0.3600	-1.8199	0.0345
0.2560	0.87715	1.6450	1.3925	0.4290	-2.1499	0.0392
0.3112	0.89605	2.0426	1.4016	0.4859	-2.4599	0.0425
0.3711	0.91603	2.5517	1.4094	0.5350	-2.7199	0.0444
0.4364	0.93728	3.2107	1.4164	0.5702	-2.8999	0.0447
0.5080	0.95990	4.0295	1.4222	0.5901	-3.0000	0.0432
0.5867	0.98446	5.0903	1.4263	0.5700	-2.9500	0.0392
0.6737	1.01075	6.4373	1.4293	0.5252	-2.7200	0.0333
0.7704	1.03947	8.1485	1.4308	0.4249	-2.2500	0.0250
0.8785	1.07081	10.5157	1.4306	0.2650	-1.2700	0.0137
1.0000	1.10577	13.3461	1.4293	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
1,2-Ethanediol + ethanol						
0.0000	0.78069	0.9891	1.3606	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
0.0503	0.79511	1.0847	1.3704	0.0879	-0.5265	0.0063
0.1025	0.81043	1.3163	1.3801	0.1529	-0.9391	0.0125
0.1565	0.82638	1.5119	1.3884	0.2182	-1.4112	0.0170
0.2125	0.84323	1.7901	1.3954	0.2680	-1.8253	0.0202
0.2707	0.86086	2.2036	1.4017	0.3142	-2.1300	0.0225
0.3310	0.87943	2.6994	1.4068	0.3498	-2.3800	0.0235
0.3937	0.89900	3.3344	1.4112	0.3751	-2.5200	0.0236
0.4589	0.91970	4.0602	1.4147	0.3862	-2.6000	0.0226
0.5268	0.94163	4.9289	1.4175	0.3822	-2.5700	0.0207
0.5975	0.96486	5.9123	1.4194	0.3643	-2.4600	0.0178
0.6712	0.98955	7.0827	1.4209	0.3292	-2.2000	0.0142
0.7480	1.01572	8.3826	1.4225	0.2822	-1.8500	0.0105
0.8283	1.04366	9.9145	1.4242	0.2141	-1.3100	0.0067
0.9122	1.07345	11.5513	1.4263	0.1288	-0.7100	0.0030
1.0000	1.10577	13.3461	1.4293	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
1,2-Ethanediol + 1-propanol						
0.0000	0.79583	1.6747	1.3816	0.0000	0.0001	0.0000
0.0647	0.81036	1.8296	1.3881	0.0572	-0.6000	0.0034
0.1296	0.82525	2.0677	1.3938	0.1306	-1.1200	0.0060
0.1949	0.84091	2.4091	1.3988	0.1862	-1.5400	0.0079
0.2604	0.85729	2.8538	1.4033	0.2326	-1.8600	0.0093
0.3262	0.87456	3.4117	1.4070	0.2602	-2.0700	0.0098
0.3923	0.89268	4.0530	1.4102	0.2772	-2.2000	0.0099
0.4586	0.91172	4.7875	1.4130	0.2830	-2.2400	0.0095

Table-3 (contd.)

0.5253	0.93172	5.6054	1.4155	0.2797	-2.2000	0.0088
0.5922	0.95274	6.5367	1.4177	0.2681	-2.0500	0.0079
0.6594	0.97488	7.5313	1.4196	0.2468	-1.8400	0.0065
0.7270	0.99832	8.5594	1.4215	0.2101	-1.6000	0.0052
0.7948	1.02309	9.7009	1.4232	0.1630	-1.2500	0.0037
0.8629	1.04922	10.8958	1.4249	0.1101	-0.8500	0.0021
0.9313	1.07666	12.1142	1.4270	0.0601	-0.4300	0.0010
1.0000	1.10577	13.3461	1.4293	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
1,2-Ethanediol + 1-butanol						
0.0000	0.80190	2.2744	1.3954	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
0.0786	0.81618	2.5246	1.3703	0.0752	-0.6200	-0.0278
0.1552	0.83101	2.8888	1.3573	0.1451	-1.1040	-0.0434
0.2299	0.84666	3.3648	1.3487	0.1863	-1.4550	-0.0545
0.3028	0.86299	3.9766	1.3462	0.2190	-1.6500	-0.0595
0.3739	0.88011	4.6477	1.3477	0.2376	-1.7660	-0.0604
0.4432	0.89805	5.3818	1.3528	0.2450	-1.8000	-0.0576
0.5110	0.91691	6.1718	1.3604	0.2381	-1.7600	-0.0523
0.5771	0.93664	7.0042	1.3695	0.2268	-1.6600	-0.0455
0.6417	0.95732	7.8795	1.3806	0.2097	-1.5000	-0.0366
0.7049	0.97904	8.7795	1.3909	0.1858	-1.2990	-0.0284
0.7666	1.00187	9.6816	1.4004	0.1558	-1.0800	-0.0210
0.8269	1.02589	10.6095	1.4094	0.1205	-0.8200	-0.0140
0.8859	1.05114	11.5225	1.4174	0.0830	-0.5600	-0.0080
0.9436	1.07767	12.4512	1.4239	0.0461	-0.2700	-0.0035
1.0000	1.10577	13.3461	1.4293	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

the mixture respectively. ($t-HC$) is the flow time adjusted by the Hagenbach correction factor,

$$HC = E/K.t^2,$$

The value $E/K = 70500$ is given in the instruction manual provided by the manufacturer. The viscometer was calibrated using double distilled water at 298.15 K. The viscometers with $t > 200$ s were selected for measurements.

The viscosity deviations of binary mixtures were calculated by using equation,

$$\Delta\eta = \eta_m - x_1\eta_1 - x_2\eta_2 \quad (3)$$

where η_m is the viscosity of the mixture, η_1 , η_2 , x_1 and x_2 is the viscosity of pure components 1 and 2, mole fraction of components 1 and 2 respectively.

The refractive index deviation of binary mixtures were calculated by using equation,

$$\Delta n_D = n_D - x_1n_{D1} - x_2n_{D2} \quad (4)$$

where n_D is the refractive index of liquid mixtures, n_{D1} and n_{D2} are refractive index of first and second

components respectively.

The calculated excess molar volumes (V^E), viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and refractive index deviations (Δn_D) reported in Table 2, were correlated by Redlich-Kister polynomial⁵, by using the relation,

$$\Delta Y = x_1x_2 \sum a_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (5)$$

The coefficients in eq. (5) were estimated by the least squares fit method and the standard deviation were calculated by using the relation,

$$\sigma = [\sum (\Delta Y_{Exp} - \Delta Y_{Calcd.})^2 / (D - N)]^{0.5} \quad (6)$$

where D and N are the number of data points and parameters, respectively.

Regression results for excess molar volumes, viscosity deviations and deviation in refractive index, of binary mixtures of 1,2-ethanediol with primary alcohols such as methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol and 1-butanol at different temperatures reported in Table 5.

The graphical variation of excess molar volume (V^E) for the binary mixtures of 1,2-ethanediol with the four primary alcohols with increasing mole fractions of 1,2-ethanediol at 303.15 K is shown in Fig. 1. The values of excess molar volumes are found to be positive for all the

Fig. 1. Variation of excess molar volume V^E against mole fraction x_1 of 1,2-ethanediol at 303.15 K : (●) methanol, (◇) ethanol, (▲) 1-propanol, (Δ) 1-butanol.

systems. For the systems where dispersion, induction and dipolar forces are operating, the values of excess molar volume are found to be positive, whereas the existence of specific interactions between the mixing components of the various binary systems tends to make excess molar volume negative^{6,7}. Since, normally dispersive interaction between unlike molecules is weaker than those between like molecules, it is reasonable that they contribute positively⁸ to V^E . The order of decrease in V^E values with respect to increase in CH_2 group is methanol < ethanol < 1-propanol < 1-butanol.

Fig. 2 shows the graphical variation of viscosity deviation ($\Delta\eta$) for the binary mixtures of 1,2-ethanediol

Fig. 2. Variation of viscosity deviations $\Delta\eta$ against mole fraction x_1 of 1,2-ethanediol at 303.15 K : (●) methanol, (◇) ethanol, (▲) 1-propanol, (Δ) 1-butanol.

with four aliphatic alcohols with increasing mole fractions of 1,2-ethanediol at 303.15 K. The values of viscosity deviations are found to be negative for all the systems. For the systems where dispersion, induction and dipolar forces are operating, the values of viscosity deviations are found to be negative⁹. Hence, mixing of like molecules results in geometrical fitting may be the factor due to which negative viscosity deviations may be observed. The negative viscosity deviations can thus be attributed to interstitial accommodation of one component into other due to differences in molecular size of mixing components. The order of decrease in $\Delta\eta$ values with respect to increase in CH_2 group is 1-butanol < 1-propanol < ethanol < methanol.

Fig. 3 shows the graphical variation of Δn_D for the binary mixtures of 1,2-ethanediol with four primary alcohols with increasing mole fractions of 1,2-ethanediol

Fig. 3. Variation of refractive index deviations Δn_D against mole fraction x_1 of 1,2-ethanediol at 303.15 K : (●) methanol, (◇) ethanol, (▲) 1-propanol, (Δ) 1-butanol.

at 303.15 K. The values of refractive index deviations are found to be positive for methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol and negative for 1-butanol systems. For the systems where dispersion, induction and dipolar forces are operating, the values of refractive index deviations are found to be positive, whereas the existence of specific interactions between the mixing components of the various binary systems tends to make refractive index deviations negative^{10,11}.

Hence in conclusion, one can say that some dispersion type interaction is observed in case of all these binary mixtures which makes the effect of dispersion forces more dominating it has been reported that since normally dispersive interaction between unlike molecules is weaker than those between like molecules.

Experimental

All the organic liquids used in the present study were of analytical reagent grade and were obtained from S.D. Fine Chemicals. They were further purified according to the procedure described in literature^{12,13}. The binary liquid mixtures were prepared by mixing known masses of pure liquids in airtight-stoppered bottles in order to minimize the evaporation losses. All measurements of mass were performed on a Mettler one pan balance (E-Mettler, Zurich), which can read up to fifth place of decimal, with an accuracy of ± 0.05 mg.

The densities of the pure liquids and their binary mixtures were measured using the single arm capillary pycnometer having bulk volume of approximately 5 cm^3 and a capillary bore with an internal diameter of 0.75 mm. The accuracy in the density measurements was found to be of $\pm 5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$.

Viscosity measurements were performed by using Schott Gerate (AVS 350) viscosity measuring equipment with a series of Ubbelohde viscometers. The uncertainty in viscosity measurement was $\pm 3 \times 10^{-3}$ mPa.s.

Refractive indices were measured with a thermostated Abbe refractometer (Focus-AR-204-85010) using the sodium D line. The uncertainty in the refractive index measurement was $\pm 3 \times 10^{-4}$. Calibration was performed by measuring the refractive indices of doubly distilled water, ethanol at defined temperature. For all the measurements, temperature was controlled by circulating the water through an ultra thermostat JULABO F-25 (made in Germany) which has an accuracy ± 0.02 °C.

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